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Overhead line and Insulated Cables

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A Study on Propagation Characteristics Degradation of High Voltage Power Cables Insulation

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SUMMARY -Power cables are of great importance in power transmission and distribution systems. Terminations and joints are the basic accessories of the power cables. They are required to make connections between lines or to an electrical apparatus. The various aspects are considered while designing the cable terminations and joints because they must possess the same integrity as their associated cables while making the connection both all indoor and outdoor applications. In cable installation, shielded power cables require electrical stress control when terminated. When the insulation shield is removed from a cable, high potential gradients are concentrated at the cutback point, causing high electrical stress. Electric field enhancement at these points can produce local discharges that could lead to either flashover along the insulation surface or dielectric breakdown causing cable failure. Cable terminations are designed to eliminate the stress concentration at the screen termination to avoid the break-down of the cable. Insulation of cable and accessories may be defected or deteriorated in installation and in use. After laying tests a diagnostic measurement should detect faults and defects caused by transports and installation. Successful measurements give fingerprint for further diagnostics during the service of the cable system. Partial discharges are one of the major reasons for degradation of cable system insulations in service. Thus, partial discharge measurement is an important diagnostic tool. Also, we will explanation the impact of Moisture with electric field forms water trees inside the insulation which may turn into electrical trees. Electrical trees are formed by partial discharges inside insulation and they will eventually lead into a breakdown of the insulation. And will study the impact of water conductivity if their water leakage in to XLPE cable insulation to do grows water tree and then the electric tree.

Keywords – Studying the reasons of insulation ageing due to treeing - Conventional applied voltage, time, frequency and temperature - Defect due to cavity with water conductivity- Partial Discharge Measurement Laboratory.

1.Introduction

Power Cable Insulation is the most crucial part of a cable as it isolates the live parts from the surroundings. The most commonly used insulation materials in extruded cables are cross linked polyethylene (XLPE), ethylene propylene Ruben (EPR) and water tree retardant cross-linked polyethylene (TR-XLPE). As the insulation ages its electric strength decreases until a final breakdown happens. Temperature, electric field and moisture are the main factors affecting insulation aging. Moisture with electric field forms water trees inside the insulation. Water trees are very harmful for solid insulation because they may turn into electrical trees. Eventually electrical trees will lead to failure. To prevent and slow down the growth of water trees different additives are added into the insulation material. From the insulation materials mentioned earlier TR-XLPE material has shown to be the most resistant to water treeing [1]. The growth rate of a water tree is typically < 1 mm/year which means that it takes about five to ten years from a water tree to grow across the whole insulation layer [2].

The insulation types of cables are Polyethylene (PE), Cross-linked Polyethylene (XLPE), Tree Retardant XLPE (TR-XLPE), Ethylene Propylene Rubber (EPR), Polyvinyl Chloride (PVC) and Chlorosulfonated Polyethylene (CSPE). Their properties can be summarized as [3,4]. Polyethylene (PE) is inexpensive produced long chain hydrocarbon. It was used in high voltage cable in the past because of its suitable electrical properties. Today, PE is used in cables at 5 kV or less because of its susceptibility to treeing at high voltages.

Cross-linked Polyethylene (XLPE) is operating good impact, abrasion, environmental stress crack resistance and good resistance to corona. The cables from 5 to 46 kV with impulse strength of 2700 V/mil use XLPE.

Tree Retardant XLPE (TR-XLPE) is an improved insulation compound in recent years and is used for medium voltage applications.

Ethylene Propylene Rubber (EPR) is commonly used in medium voltage applications yet can be used for low voltage cables. It has good elastic properties, low temperature resistance, environmental and ozone resistance.

Polyvinyl Chloride (PVC) has good electrical properties and is resistant to flame, moisture and abrasion. However, it's not recommended for temperatures lower than -10°C because it stiffens as temperatures decline. High dielectric constant also disadvantaging of the compound. It's the most common insulation for cables rated at 1000 volts or less. Chlorosulfonated Polyethylene (CSPE) has a trade name called "Hypalon". It's a rubbery polymer having tensile strength and abrasion, oil, chemical resistance that can be rated at 90°C . Its properties differ depending on the quantity and type of materials comprised.

2.Moisture proofing

Moisture has a negative effect on cables lifetime. This is why water tight structures are used in extruded cables. Radial water tightness can be achieved by using e.g. laminated aluminum foil attached to the inner surface of a jacket. At the same time, this kind of layer can work as a metallic shield. Semi-conductive swelling tapes, powders or strings inside the cable structure are used as longitudinal water blocks. A cable is aged in different ways because of moisture Corrosion damages the metallic shield and in the worst case it might break its continuity Moisture with electric field forms water trees inside the insulation which may turn into electrical trees. Electrical trees are formed by partial discharges inside insulation and they will eventually lead into a breakdown of the insulation.

3. Conventional PD detection method

Is standardized method based on international standard IEC 60270 [5,6]. Partial discharges that occur in the test object will produce current or voltage pulses. In contrast to the well-established PD measuring method according to IEC 60270 the described system operates in the UHF frequency domain, hence the derived and evaluated output PD pulse magnitude is more or less a measure of the PD current amplitude and not for the apparent charge as defined in the above-mentioned standard [7]. This method based on measurement of the charge displacement q , expressed in (pC), from the pulses which generated from partial discharge. Figure (1) shows the test set-up for 30 kV test voltage and PD measurements according to IEC 60502-2 [4]. The tests are carried out in the Extra High Voltage Research Centre (EHVRC) PD Lab. In these PD measurements, 50Hz continuous AC voltage is used as an energizing method. The PD detector consists of several important components: regulator transformer, high voltage reactor, high voltage filter, coupling capacitor, digital universal measuring instrument and PD detector (TE571). Calibration of PD measuring instrument is important factor to ensure that the PD measuring system is able to measure the PD magnitude properly. Calibration is done by injecting a short duration current pulse of known charge from the calibrator to the terminal of test object while the measuring system is de-energized. Using this PD detector several important parameters of PD occurrence can be obtained such as :

- PD inception voltage (PDIV)
- PD magnitude in pC at PDIV
- PD magnitude as a function of voltage applied
- PD pattern

Figure 1 : Basic coupling mode in series with the test object capacitor [8]

4. Treeing Phenomena

Electrical treeing degradation has history as the development of paper/ oil insulation system. It has been observed in organic as well as polymeric materials and hence there must be some mechanism of development of the tree which is independent of the chemical nature of the material. Water tree was recognized during early 1970s, [1], and hence another cause of premature failure in polymeric insulating material was known. A cable tree has been defined as 'latent damage in the insulation that consists of microscopic channels formed by partial breakdown of defective or overstressed region' and 'hollow tubes with non-conducting walls and containing the gaseous products of discharge' [2]. A tree is an electrical pre-breakdown phenomenon in the insulation of a cable. The term is used to describe the type of damage that progresses through a dielectric section under electrical stress, which resembles the form of a tree. Trees are classified based on different criteria such as shape, location of origination, and other characteristics. Based on shape, trees can be classified as Broccoli, Strings, Delta, Bow tie, Plumes, Dendrites, Spikes and Fans. Trees can be classified as two major classes : electrical (dry) trees and water (wet) trees. This is a common classification of trees Electrical trees can be characterized as consisting of a hollow channel resulting from the decomposition of material, clearly visible in translucent or transparent solid dielectrics when examined with an optical microscope and transmitted light. A water tree is characterized not by permanent hollow

channels, but by very fine filamentary paths between small cavities through which moisture has penetrated under the action of a voltage gradient.

4.1 Water Tree

Penetration of moisture is highly affected by the presence of electric field. Water trees initiate at a point of electric stress and grow parallel to the electric field lines. The growth of a water tree causes a reduction of the effective insulation thickness below the point that is required to withstand the electric stress, after which electrical tree causes the cable to fail. It was observed that the growth rate of wet trees increases with the conductivity of water [9]. Thus, the presence of conductive water and voltage stress are the fundamental requirements for the initiation and growth of water trees. However aging time, material nature, contaminants, operating temperature, and cable design are also factors affecting the initiation and growth of water trees.

Three quantitative concept models were developed to express the three types of water trees. The different water trees are shown in Figures 2.1 and 2.2 VDP response is given by bush trees and bow-tie trees. TLC or LC responses are shown when water trees have grown through the insulation [10].

Figure 2.1,2.2 : XLPE cable deteriorated by leakage and bush trees [1]

4.2 Electrical Tree

An electrical (dry) tree is also found to grow in a region of high electrical stress, such as metallic asperities, conducting contaminants, and structural irregularities. Partial discharge in voids can also generate degradation structures from the void surface. Those trees, which are initiated at electrode, are termed as vented trees. An electrical tree has three phases. First is the initiation phase, second is the growth or propagation phase, and third is the breakdown phase. No partial discharge occurs during the initial phase. During the propagation phase the tree propagates by continuous partial discharge activity, and cable insulation fails during breakdown phase.

There are basically two shapes of electrical trees bush- and branch-like and it depends on the average voltage stress which shape forms. If the average voltage stress is <math><3\text{ to }5\text{ kV/mm}</math>, then forming trees will be branch-like. When voltage stress is >math>>3\text{ to }5\text{ kV/mm}</math> bush-like electrical trees are formed. Usually electrical trees spotted from medium voltage extruded cables are branch-like but also bush-like trees can be found. The transition between branch- and bush-like trees is not sharp. At intermediate voltages, the tree starts off as a bush-like and then converts to a branch-like [11]. Figures (3 and 3.1) present an example of a bush-like -and a branch-like electrical tree.

Figure 3,3.1. : Branch-like electrical tree [12]

4.2.1 Initiation of Electrical Tree

The electrical stress produced at a stress concentration site such as metallic asperities, conducting contaminations, and structural irregularities in the insulation become significantly large to initiate partial discharge in a very small cavity located near the tip. Breakdown of gas occurs within the cavity with the help of initiatory electrons [13]. These electrons are provided by natural radiation in the case of large sized cavities, these electrons are provided by natural radiation in the case of large sized cavities, the cavities will provide a large number of these electrons in small size cavities. The partial discharge will produce a rapid erosion of the insulation, producing discharge channels, which terminate at the needle tip and result in a visible electrical tree. Laboratory tests with the needles in solids deny the requirement of the presence of an initial void to start a tree [14]. Electrical stress concentration, produced on rough or sharp edges of electrodes, and also on sharp edges of conducting contaminant particles, and high and divergent electric fields, is always necessary to initiate an electrical tree.

4.2.2 Growth of Electrical Tree

The growth mechanism of electrical trees can be described as an array of fine erosion channels formed through a partial discharge (PD) activity within the evolving tree structure starting at the void or the tip of the needle [15]. Partial discharge causes the decomposition of insulation to gases. Various researches prove that the voltage stress at the tip of an electrical discharge depends on the characteristics of the gas formed, which depends on the material and local temperature produced by the discharge, rather than on the shape of the electrodes that originated it. Chemically the growth of an electrical tree can be described as the transfer of energy between ions and surrounding walls when the gas formed in a cavity is ionized to form plasma. An electron avalanche is formed in some conditions, which enhances the effect further [16]. As the purpose of this study is to study the failure of XLPE cable across dry regions, water treeing is not the focus. This research work concentrates on modeling the aging procedure caused due to the growth of an electrical tree. Lab methods have been developed to age the cable in hot and dry conditions and to analyze the structural changes and changes in the electrical breakdown strength of the cable [17]. Data collected previously using these methods is used in this thesis to develop a multivariate analysis technique is developed in this thesis to predict the remaining life of a cable.

5. Defect due to cavity with water conductivity

Figures (4.4.1,4.2,4.3,4.4) show the test setup and Figures (5.20a to 5.20l) show the phase-position quantities $H_{qmax}(\varphi)$, $H_{qn}(\varphi)$ and $H_n(\varphi, q)$ calculated for the sample cable 18/30 kV-1x70 mm² discussed and the display a 3-dimensional relationship between discharge magnitude, discharge intensity and phase angle the $H_n(\varphi, q)$ distribution is used. It shows that the maximum discharge magnitude is about 2.6 pC at without cavity, the maximum discharge magnitude is about 22 pC at artificial spherical cavity depth 2mm in the XLPE insulation with water conductivity 1000 μ MHOS, the maximum discharge magnitude is 132 pC at spherical cavity depth 2mm in the XLPE insulation with water conductivity 2000 μ MHOS, the maximum discharge magnitude is about 265 pC at spherical cavity depth 2mm in the XLPE insulation with water conductivity 3000 μ MHOS, the maximum discharge magnitude is 1.9 nC at spherical cavity depth 2mm in the XLPE insulation with water conductivity 4000 μ MHOS, and the maximum discharge magnitude is 11 nC at spherical cavity depth 2mm in the XLPE insulation with water conductivity 5000 μ MHOS, There are more discharge quantities in the positive half of power voltage cycle than that in negative half. And the number of discharges in the positive half is more than that in the negative half. From the discharge phase-position distribution, and this figure shows the PD quantities maximum discharge magnitude $q_{max}(t)$ and the number of pulses/second as observed during 2 minutes test time.

Figure 4 : Test setup for the cable sample 18/30 kV-1x70mm² with artificial cavities at immersed in the different water conductivity

Figure 4.1: Test setup for the cable sample 18/30 kV-1x70mm² with artificial cavities at immersed in the different water conductivity

Figure 4.2: With spherical cavity 2mm at conductivity 1000 μMHOS

Figure 4.3: With spherical cavity 2mm at conductivity 5000 μMHOS

Figure 4.4. : PD measurements for cable sample 1x70 mm² – 18/30 kV with different water conductivity at the constant artificial spherical cavity diameter 4 mm² and constant depth 2mm

The growth mechanism of electrical trees can be increase with increasing KV level with short time as showing in the Figure (5).

Figure 5 : Electrical Tree for cable sample 1x70 mm² – 18/30 kV with constant artificial spherical cavity diameter 4 mm² and constant depth 2mm

6. Different characteristics of Water trees and Electrical trees

Water Trees	Electrical Trees
Water required	Water not required
Fan or bush shaped	Needle or spindle shaped
Grow for years	Failure shortly after formation
Micro-voids connected by tracks	Carbonized regions

Table 1 : Comparison between Water Tree & Electrical Tree for cable 1x70 mm² – 18/30 kV with different water conductivity at the constant artificial spherical cavity diameter 4 mm² and constant depth 2mm.

7.CONCLUSION

I-The experiments showed that growth of cavities between the insulation results in a decrease of the dielectric strength and that breakdown occurs along the cavities. The effect of increasing the interfacial pressure in a cable is probably to limit the extension of cavities between the insulation and therefore prevent the large reduction of the dielectric strength along the interfaces.

II-The laboratory experiments showed that the level of partial discharge increases with increasing conductivity of the water in the case of cavities.

-As a result, combining between the water tree & electrical tree

A -The water tree it will growth of a water tree causes a reduction of the effective insulation thickness diagnosis can be of benefit by insulation condition assessment of distribution power cable networks.

B -The electrical tree an electrical (dry) tree is also found to grow in a region of high electrical stress,

III-The growth mechanism of electrical trees can be increase with increasing KV level with short time

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